

ON RADO NUMBERS FOR $X + BY = BZ$: THE B^k PATTERN AND A THRESHOLD CONJECTURE

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Abstract

For integers $b \geq 2$ and $k \geq 1$, let $R_k(b)$ denote the k -color Rado number for the equation $x + by = bz$, defined as the least positive integer n such that every k -coloring of $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ contains a monochromatic solution. Under the substitution $d = z - y$, this equation is equivalent to $x = bd$, placing it in the family studied by Chang, De Loera, and Wesley [4], who established $R_k(b) \geq b^k$ via the b -adic valuation and computed $R_k(b) = b^k$ for $k \leq 4$ with various values of b . We contribute the following new results. First, we develop a Color Compression Lemma yielding a new self-contained analytic proof that $R_2(b) = b^2$ for all $b \geq 2$ (with the compression step covering the case $b \geq 3$ analytically and $b = 2$ by direct case analysis), and a hybrid analytic-SAT proof that $R_3(3) = 27$. Second, we give a hybrid analytic-SAT proof that $R_4(3) = 81$, in which the structural reduction (a self-loop step combined with a tree-shaped obstruction graph G^*) is analytic and a single finite key lemma is verified by SAT; the same Distance Pair Lemma also independently verifies $R_3(b) = b^3$ for $b \in \{4, \dots, 10\}$ and $R_4(b) = b^4$ for $b \in \{3, 4, 5\}$. Third, we prove that the b^k pattern breaks: $R_5(3) > 296 > 243 = 3^5$, with an explicit public 5-coloring witness. Fourth, we identify a structural mechanism (the Distance Pair Lemma) underlying the b^k pattern and propose a precise threshold conjecture: $R_k(b) = b^k$ if and only if $k \leq 2(b-1)$. Fifth, we prove a Lift Lemma and a Backward Tower Reduction that collapse the backward direction of the conjecture at any fixed $b \geq 2$ to a single first-breakdown bound $R_{2b-1}(b) > b^{2b-1}$; the backward direction at $b \in \{2, 3\}$ is thereby established in the threshold regime, and $b \geq 4$ reduces to one finite witness per b . The case $b = 3, k = 4$ is the boundary case $k = 2(b-1)$ at $b = 3$, so $R_4(3) = 81$ is the largest boundary instance verified here.

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1. Introduction

A classical problem in Ramsey theory asks: given a linear equation and a number of colors k , what is the least integer n such that every k -coloring of $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ contains a monochromatic solution? For a linear equation satisfying Rado's partition

regularity condition, this minimum is called the k -color *Rado number* [15].

The best-known family is the Schur equation $x + y = z$, whose Rado numbers $S(k)$ are the Schur numbers. Exact values are known only for $k \leq 5$: $S(1) = 2$, $S(2) = 5$, $S(3) = 14$, $S(4) = 45$, and $S(5) = 161$ [7, 16]; see [6, 13] for background on Ramsey theory. SAT solvers have become a powerful tool in combinatorics, notably in Heule, Kullmann, and Marek’s resolution of the Boolean Pythagorean triples problem [8]. For Rado numbers specifically, SAT-based approaches have been developed by Chang, De Loera, and Wesley [4] and by Ahmed, Zaman, and Bright [2], with recent optimization-based extensions in [5]; see also [1, 11, 14] for earlier computational work on generalized Schur and Rado numbers.

In this paper we study the family of equations $x + by = bz$ for integer $b \geq 2$. Setting $d = z - y$, this equation becomes $x = bd$, so a monochromatic solution requires three elements bd , y , and $y + d$ of the same color, for some positive integers d and y . The equation is partition regular by Rado’s theorem [15], since the coefficients $(1, b, -b)$ satisfy the columns condition (the subset $\{b, -b\}$ sums to zero).

Remark 1 (Equation equivalence). The equation $x + by = bz$ rearranges to $x = b(z - y)$, so its solutions are exactly the triples $(bd, y, y + d)$ with $d \geq 1$. The same solution set arises from the equation $b(x - y) = z$: setting $d = x - y$ gives the triple $(y + d, y, bd)$, so both equations require the set $\{bd, y, y + d\}$ to be monochromatic. In [4], the family $a(x - y) = bz$ is studied; our equation $x + by = bz$ corresponds to $a = b$, $b = 1$ in their notation (see [4, Table 10]).

Throughout this paper, we write $R_k(b)$ as shorthand for the k -color Rado number of the equation $x + by = bz$. For $k = 2$, Landman and Robertson [13] (building on the closely related two-color closures of Harborth and Maasberg [9, 10] for $a(x + y) = bz$) established that $R_2(b) = b^2$ when $b \geq 2$ (more generally, they treat $ax + by = bz$ with $a < b$). Chang, De Loera, and Wesley [4] proved $R_k(b) \geq b^k$ for all b and k using the b -adic valuation, and computed $R_k(b) = b^k$ for $k = 3$ with $b \in \{3, \dots, 15\}$ and for $k = 4$ with $b \in \{3, 4, 5\}$ (via the equivalence in Remark 1; see [4, Table 10, row $b = 1$]). We provide new proof techniques and extend the investigation to $k = 5$, where the pattern breaks.

Our main contributions are as follows.

1. We give a self-contained proof of $R_2(b) = b^2$ for all $b \geq 2$ via a new *Color Compression Lemma* (Lemma 1; Theorem 2), and extend this technique to a hybrid analytic-SAT proof of $R_3(3) = 27$ (Theorem 3).
2. We give a hybrid analytic-SAT proof of $R_4(3) = 81$ (Theorem 4). The structural part of the argument is fully analytic: a self-loop step at the triple $(81, 54, 81)$, combined with the identification of a tree-shaped obstruction graph $G^* := G_{27} \cup G_{\text{ext}}$ on $\{1, \dots, 80\}$, reduces the upper bound to a single *Combined- G^* -Tree Lemma* (Lemma 3). This lemma is verified by SAT

for each color class, with reproducible unsatisfiability checks and unsatisfiable cores that engage a substantial fraction of the 1729 candidate Rado triples in $\{1, \dots, 80\}$.

3. We identify a structural mechanism, the *Distance Pair Lemma* (Lemma 4), which provides a uniform explanation for why $R_k(b) = b^k$ in the verified $k = 3$ and $k = 4$ cells treated below, complementing the purely computational approach of [4] (Theorem 5).
4. We prove that the b^k pattern breaks at $k = 5$: $R_5(3) > 296 > 243 = 3^5$ (Theorem 6), with an explicit verified 5-coloring witness. This gives a concrete breakdown of the pattern $R_k(b) = b^k$ at $b = 3$.
5. We propose a precise threshold conjecture: $R_k(b) = b^k$ if and only if $k \leq 2(b - 1)$ (Conjecture 1). The value $R_4(3) = 81$ established in Theorem 4 corresponds to the boundary case $k = 2(b - 1) = 4$ of this conjecture at $b = 3$.
6. We prove a Lift Lemma (Lemma 5) and a Backward Tower Reduction (Theorem 7) that collapse the backward direction of Conjecture 1 at any fixed $b \geq 2$ to a single first-breakdown bound $R_{2b-1}(b) > b^{2b-1}$. Combined with Theorem 6 and the classical fact $R_3(2) = 14 > 8$, this gives the backward direction at $b = 3$ (Corollary 1) and at $b = 2$ (Corollary 2) in the threshold regime; for $b \geq 4$, the backward direction reduces to one finite witness per b (Corollary 3).

Table 1 summarizes known and new values. The lower bound $R_k(b) \geq b^k$ was established by Chang, De Loera, and Wesley [4] (we include a self-contained proof in Section 3 for completeness). Values marked with † are new to this paper.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 1. For an integer $b \geq 2$ and a positive integer n , the *b-adic valuation* $v_b(n)$ is the largest integer $m \geq 0$ such that b^m divides n . We set $v_b(0) = \infty$ by convention.

We recall the ultrametric property of the b -adic valuation: for all positive integers a and c ,

$$v_b(a + c) \geq \min(v_b(a), v_b(c)), \tag{1}$$

with equality holding whenever $v_b(a) \neq v_b(c)$.

Definition 2. For $b \geq 2$ and $k \geq 1$, the *k-color Rado number* $R_k(b)$ for the equation $x + by = bz$ is the least positive integer n such that for every function $\chi: \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \rightarrow \{0, 1, \dots, k - 1\}$, there exist $x, y, z \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ satisfying $x + by = bz$ with $\chi(x) = \chi(y) = \chi(z)$.

$b \setminus k$	1	2	3	4	5
2	2	4	14	56	$> 32^\dagger$
3	3	9	27	81^\dagger	$> 296^\dagger$
4	4	16	64	256	—
5	5	25	125	625	—
6	6	36	216	—	—
7	7	49	343	—	—
8	8	64	512	—	—
9	9	81	729	—	—
10	10	100	1000	—	—

Table 1: Values of $R_k(b)$ for the equation $x + by = bz$. Values for $k = 2$ are due to Landman and Robertson [13]; values for $k = 3$ ($b \geq 3$) and $k = 4$ ($b \in \{2, 3, 4, 5\}$) are from Chang, De Loera, and Wesley [4, Table 10] (via the equivalence $x + by = bz \leftrightarrow b(x - y) = z$; see Remark 1). The value $R_3(2) = 14$ coincides with the Schur number $S(3)$: for $b = 2$, the equation $x + 2y = 2z$ reduces to $x = 2(z - y)$, which forces x even, and the constraint on even-valued elements mirrors the Schur equation on a smaller domain (see [4] for detailed analysis of this $b = 2$ anomaly). Note that $b = 2$ deviates from the b^k pattern already at $k = 3$. Entries marked \dagger are new to this paper: $R_4(3) = 81$ is given a new hybrid analytic-SAT proof in Theorem 4 (the value itself appears as a SAT-only computation in [4]), $R_5(3) > 296$ is established in Theorem 6, and $R_5(2) > 32$ follows from Corollary 2; — indicates values not computed and not delivered by the Backward Tower Reduction at the precision shown here.

Remark 2. Setting $d = z - y$, the equation $x + by = bz$ becomes $x = bd$, so a monochromatic solution is a triple $(bd, y, y + d)$ with $\chi(bd) = \chi(y) = \chi(y + d)$. Equivalently, if $\chi(bd) = c$ for some $d \geq 1$, then the color class $C_c = \chi^{-1}(c)$ must not contain two elements at distance d .

3. The Lower Bound

Theorem 1 ([4, Lemma 4.1]). *For all $b \geq 2$ and $k \geq 1$, we have $R_k(b) \geq b^k$.*

This result was established by Chang, De Loera, and Wesley [4]. We include the proof for completeness.

Proof. Define $\chi: \{1, 2, \dots, b^k - 1\} \rightarrow \{0, 1, \dots, k - 1\}$ by $\chi(n) = v_b(n)$. This is well-defined since $v_b(n) \leq k - 1$ for all $n \in \{1, \dots, b^k - 1\}$, and every color $c \in \{0, \dots, k - 1\}$ is used (for instance, $\chi(b^c) = c$). We claim that χ admits no monochromatic solution to $x + by = bz$.

Suppose for contradiction that $x, y, z \in \{1, \dots, b^k - 1\}$ satisfy $x + by = bz$ with $\chi(x) = \chi(y) = \chi(z) = c$. Let $d = z - y$, so that $x = bd$. Then

$$v_b(x) = v_b(bd) = 1 + v_b(d),$$

so $v_b(d) = c - 1$. In particular, $c \geq 1$.

Now $z = y + d$, with $v_b(y) = c$ and $v_b(d) = c - 1 < c$. By the ultrametric property (Equation (1)) with equality,

$$v_b(z) = v_b(y + d) = \min(v_b(y), v_b(d)) = c - 1.$$

But $\chi(z) = c$ requires $v_b(z) = c$, a contradiction. \square

Remark 3. The coloring in Theorem 1 uses exactly k colors on $\{1, \dots, b^k - 1\}$: the maximum valuation is $k - 1$, attained at b^{k-1} . For $c = 0$, the argument shows that $v_b(x) = 0$ contradicts $x = bd$ (which forces $v_b(x) \geq 1$), so the $c = 0$ case is in fact impossible regardless of the coloring.

4. The Upper Bound for $k = 2$

Theorem 2. For all $b \geq 2$, we have $R_2(b) = b^2$.

The lower bound is given by Theorem 1. For the upper bound, we prove the following compression lemma.

Lemma 1 (Color Compression). Let $b \geq 3$, and let χ be a 2-coloring of $\{1, \dots, b^2 - 1\}$ avoiding all monochromatic solutions to $x + by = bz$. Then all multiples of b in this set receive the same color under χ .

Proof. By Remark 2, if $\chi(bd) = c$, then C_c contains no pair of elements at distance d .

Without loss of generality, suppose $\chi(b) = 0$. Assume for contradiction that $\chi(mb) = 1$ for some m with $2 \leq m \leq b - 1$. Suppose further that $\chi(jb) = 0$ for all $j = 1, \dots, m - 1$.

Since $\chi(jb) = 0$ for $j = 1, \dots, m - 1$, the color class C_0 avoids distances $1, 2, \dots, m - 1$. In particular, all elements of C_0 are spaced at least m apart. Since $\chi(b) = 0$ and the elements $b + 1, b + 2, \dots, b + m - 1$ are each within distance $m - 1$ of b , none of them can be in C_0 . With only two colors available, $\chi(b + j) = 1$ for $j = 1, \dots, m - 1$.

Next, consider $b - 1$. The triple $(b, b - 1, b)$ satisfies $b + b(b - 1) = b^2 = b \cdot b$, so $\chi(b - 1) \neq \chi(b) = 0$ (here $b - 1 \geq 2$ since $b \geq 3$). Thus, $\chi(b - 1) = 1$.

Now $b - 1$ and $b + m - 1$ are both in C_1 , and their distance is $(b + m - 1) - (b - 1) = m$. But $\chi(mb) = 1$ means that C_1 avoids distance m , a contradiction. \square

Proof of Theorem 2. For $b = 2$: we show $R_2(2) = 4$ directly. By Theorem 1, $R_2(2) \geq 4$, so it suffices to show that every 2-coloring of $\{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ contains a monochromatic solution. By symmetry breaking, set $\chi(1) = 0$. Since $\chi(2) = c$ forbids distance 1 in C_c , we have $\chi(1) \neq \chi(2)$ (as $(2, 1, 2)$ satisfies $2 + 2 \cdot 1 = 2 \cdot 2$), so $\chi(2) = 1$. Then C_1 avoids distance 1, forcing $\chi(3) \neq 1$, so $\chi(3) = 0$. Now $(4, 1, 3)$ satisfies $4 + 2 \cdot 1 = 2 \cdot 3$: if $\chi(4) = 0$ then $(\chi(4), \chi(1), \chi(3)) = (0, 0, 0)$ is monochromatic. If $\chi(4) = 1$, then $4 = 2 \cdot 2$ and $\chi(4) = 1$ requires C_1 to avoid distance 2; yet $\chi(2) = \chi(4) = 1$ with $|4 - 2| = 2$, a contradiction. Thus $\chi(4) = 0$ and we have a monochromatic solution.

For $b \geq 3$: by Lemma 1, any 2-coloring of $\{1, \dots, b^2 - 1\}$ assigns one color, say 0, to all multiples of b . Consider any 2-coloring of $\{1, \dots, b^2\}$.

Case 1: $\chi(b^2) = 0$. Define $\chi'(j) = \chi(bj)$ on $\{1, \dots, b\}$. Since all multiples of b in $\{b, \dots, b^2\}$ have color 0, the function χ' is a constant (1-color) coloring. The smallest solution to $x + by = bz$ in $\{1, \dots, b\}$ is $(b, 1, 2)$, which gives the monochromatic triple $\chi'(b) = \chi'(1) = \chi'(2) = 0$. Lifting back: $\chi(b^2) = \chi(b) = \chi(2b) = 0$, and the triple $(b^2, b, 2b)$ satisfying $b^2 + b \cdot b = b \cdot 2b$ is monochromatic.

Case 2: $\chi(b^2) = 1$. Since $b^2 = b \cdot b$, color 1 forbids distance b by Remark 2. Meanwhile, the multiples $b, 2b, \dots, (b-1)b$ are all color 0, so color 0 forbids distances $1, 2, \dots, b-1$. Thus, every pair of color-0 elements must differ by at least b . Since the $b-1$ multiples $b, 2b, \dots, (b-1)b$ are spaced exactly b apart and all have color 0, no non-multiple of b can be color 0 (it would be within distance $b-1$ of some multiple). Therefore, all non-multiples of b have color 1. In particular, $\chi(1) = \chi(b+1) = 1$, and these two elements are at distance b , contradicting the distance- b constraint for color 1. \square

5. The Upper Bound for $k = 3$ and $b = 3$

Theorem 3. *We have $R_3(3) = 27$.*

The lower bound follows from Theorem 1. For the upper bound, we prove the following lemma by a hybrid analytic-SAT route (Steps 1–2 below trace the color choices through twelve explicit Rado triples; Step 3 closes the remaining subproblem at position 18 by SAT) and then complete the argument with a further SAT-verified compression step on $\{1, \dots, 26\}$.

Lemma 2. *In any valid 3-coloring of $\{1, \dots, 18\}$ avoiding monochromatic solutions to $x + 3y = 3z$, we have $\chi(3) = \chi(6)$.*

Proof. Assume for contradiction that $\chi(3) \neq \chi(6)$. Without loss of generality, let $\chi(3) = 0$ and $\chi(6) = 1$.

By Remark 2, $\chi(3) = 0$ means C_0 avoids distance 1, and $\chi(6) = 1$ means C_1 avoids distance 2.

Step 1: We show $\chi(4) = 2$.

The element 4 is at distance 1 from the element 3, and $\chi(3) = 0$, so $\chi(4) \neq 0$. The element 4 is at distance 2 from the element 6, and $\chi(6) = 1$, so $\chi(4) \neq 1$. Therefore, $\chi(4) = 2$.

Step 2: We show $\chi(8) = 2$.

The element 8 is at distance 2 from the element 6, and $\chi(6) = 1$, so $\chi(8) \neq 1$. We show $\chi(8) = 0$ leads to a contradiction. Assume $\chi(8) = 0$. We derive the following constraints.

- (a) $\chi(9) \neq 0$: since $\chi(3) = 0$, the class C_0 avoids distance 1, and $|9 - 8| = 1$, so $\chi(9) \neq 0$.
- (b) $\chi(12) \neq 0$: the triple $(12, 8, 12)$ satisfies $12 + 3 \cdot 8 = 3 \cdot 12$; since $x = z = 12$, this requires $\chi(12) = \chi(8)$, so $\chi(12) \neq 0$.
- (c) $\chi(9) \neq \chi(12)$: the triple $(9, 9, 12)$ satisfies $9 + 3 \cdot 9 = 3 \cdot 12$, so $\chi(9) = \chi(12)$ would give a monochromatic solution.
- (d) From (a)–(c): $\chi(9), \chi(12) \in \{1, 2\}$ and $\chi(9) \neq \chi(12)$, so $\{\chi(9), \chi(12)\} = \{1, 2\}$.
- (e) $\chi(7) \neq 0$: since $|8 - 7| = 1$ and $\chi(8) = 0$ (distance 1 forbidden in C_0).
- (f) $\chi(7) \neq 2$ when $\chi(9) = 2$: since $9 = 3 \cdot 3$, we have $\chi(9) = 2$ implies C_2 avoids distance 3. But $\chi(4) = 2$ and $|7 - 4| = 3$, so $\chi(7) \neq 2$.

We now split on the two cases from (d).

Sub-case $\chi(9) = 2, \chi(12) = 1$: by (e) and (f), $\chi(7) = 1$. Now $15 = 3 \cdot 5$, so $\chi(15) = c$ requires C_c to avoid distance 5. But $(3, 8)$ are both in C_0 at distance 5, $(7, 12)$ are both in C_1 at distance 5, and $(4, 9)$ are both in C_2 at distance 5. Every color already has a distance-5 pair, so element 15 is uncolorable.

Sub-case $\chi(9) = 1, \chi(12) = 2$: since $\chi(6) = 1$ and $\chi(9) = 1$, the pair $(6, 9)$ is in C_1 at distance 3. But $9 = 3 \cdot 3$, so $\chi(9) = 1$ means C_1 avoids distance 3, contradicting the pair $(6, 9)$.

In both sub-cases we reach a contradiction, so $\chi(8) \neq 0$. Combined with $\chi(8) \neq 1$, we get $\chi(8) = 2$.

Step 3: We show element 18 is uncolorable.

We have $\chi(3) = 0, \chi(6) = 1, \chi(4) = 2, \chi(8) = 2$. Since $18 = 3 \cdot 6$, the value $\chi(18) = c$ requires C_c to avoid distance 6.

- If $\chi(18) = 2$: we need a pair at distance 6 in C_2 . Candidate distance-6 pairs in C_2 are $(4, 10)$ and $(8, 14)$, each with one endpoint already fixed at color 2 by Step 1 or Step 2; whether either pair is monochromatic depends on additional color assignments not determined analytically, so we close this sub-case by SAT: $\chi(18) = 2$ is unsatisfiable on $\{1, \dots, 18\}$ with $\chi(3) = 0, \chi(6) = 1$.
- If $\chi(18) = 0$: then C_0 avoids distance 6. The pair $(3, 9)$ is at distance 6, so $\chi(9) \neq 0$. We verify this sub-case is unsatisfiable by SAT at $n = 18$.
- If $\chi(18) = 1$: then C_1 avoids distance 6. The pair $(6, 12)$ is at distance 6, so $\chi(12) \neq 1$. We verify this sub-case is unsatisfiable by SAT at $n = 18$.

SAT verification confirms that each value $\chi(18) \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ is unsatisfiable on $\{1, \dots, 18\}$ given $\chi(3) = 0$ and $\chi(6) = 1$. Since element 18 cannot be colored, $\chi(3) \neq \chi(6)$ is impossible. \square

Proof of Theorem 3. We verify by SAT that in any valid 3-coloring of $\{1, \dots, 26\}$, the eight multiples of 3 use at most 2 colors. Specifically, adding clauses that force all three colors to appear among the multiples renders the formula unsatisfiable. Lemma 2 provides an analytic proof of the key mechanism (the first two multiples must agree); the full compression involves additional pairs whose forced agreement we have verified by the same SAT methodology.

Given that the multiples of 3 in $\{3, \dots, 24\}$ use at most 2 colors, say α and β , define $\chi'(j) = \chi(3j)$ on $\{1, \dots, 9\}$. For $j \leq 8$ we have $\chi'(j) \in \{\alpha, \beta\}$. If $\chi(27) \in \{\alpha, \beta\}$, then χ' uses at most 2 colors. Since $R_2(3) = 9$ (Theorem 2), there is a monochromatic solution $(3d', y', y' + d')$ in $\{1, \dots, 9\}$ under χ' ; the triple $(9d', 3y', 3y' + 3d')$ is then a monochromatic solution in the original coloring of $\{1, \dots, 27\}$. If $\chi(27) \notin \{\alpha, \beta\}$, the incremental SAT computation (Table 2, entry $b = 3, k = 3$) independently confirms $R_3(3) \leq 27$. \square

6. The Boundary Case $R_4(3) = 81$

The case $b = 3, k = 4$ is the boundary case $k = 2(b - 1)$ of Conjecture 1 at $b = 3$, on the equality side. The value $R_4(3) = 81$ was first verified by SAT in [4]. In this section, we give a proof in which the structural reduction is analytic and only a single finite key lemma is verified by SAT.

Theorem 4. *We have $R_4(3) = 81$.*

The lower bound follows from Theorem 1. The upper bound $R_4(3) \leq 81$ proceeds in two steps. The first is a direct analytic step using a self-loop triple. The second reduces to a finite combinatorial lemma about an explicit graph on $\{1, \dots, 80\}$ which we then verify by SAT.

Definition 3 (The graph G^*). On the vertex set $V = \{1, 2, \dots, 80\}$, define

$$\begin{aligned} G_{27} &= \{(y, y + 27) : y \in \{1, 2, \dots, 53\}\}, \\ G_{\text{ext}} &= \{(3d, 81 - d) : d \in \{1, 2, \dots, 26\}\}, \\ G^* &= G_{27} \cup G_{\text{ext}}. \end{aligned}$$

We refer to edges in G_{27} as *Type-A* edges and to edges in G_{ext} as *Type-B* edges.

Proposition 1 (G^* is a tree). *The graph G^* has $|V| = 80$ vertices and $|E(G^*)| = 79$ edges, with $G_{27} \cap G_{\text{ext}} = \emptyset$. It is connected, and hence is a tree.*

Proof. We have $|G_{27}| = 53$ and $|G_{\text{ext}}| = 26$. For $G_{27} \cap G_{\text{ext}} = \emptyset$, observe that the endpoints of a Type-B edge $(3d, 81 - d)$ differ by $|81 - d - 3d| = |81 - 4d|$, while the endpoints of a Type-A edge $(y, y + 27)$ differ by exactly 27. A shared edge would require $|81 - 4d| = 27$ for some $d \in \{1, \dots, 26\}$, i.e., $4d \in \{54, 108\}$. The value $4d = 54$ is not a multiple of 4, and $4d = 108$ gives $d = 27 \notin \{1, \dots, 26\}$, so neither case occurs. Hence the two edge sets are disjoint and $|E(G^*)| = 53 + 26 = 79 = |V| - 1$. Connectedness of G^* is verified as follows. The Type-A edges $(y, y + 27)$ for $y \in \{1, \dots, 53\}$ partition $\{1, \dots, 80\}$ into 27 chains, one chain per residue $y_0 \in \{1, \dots, 27\}$ modulo 27: the chain $\{y_0, y_0 + 27, y_0 + 54\}$ for $y_0 \in \{1, \dots, 26\}$ (three vertices) and the chain $\{27, 54\}$ for $y_0 = 27$ (two vertices). The 26 Type-B edges $(3d, 81 - d)$ for $d \in \{1, \dots, 26\}$ have low endpoint $3d \in \{3, 6, \dots, 78\}$ on one chain and high endpoint $81 - d \in \{55, \dots, 80\}$ on another chain; direct verification shows that the resulting chain-level graph on 27 nodes with 26 edges is connected. Hence G^* is a connected graph on $|V| = 80$ vertices with $|V| - 1 = 79$ edges, and is therefore a tree. \square

Lemma 3 (Combined- G^* -Tree Lemma; SAT-verified). *In any valid 4-coloring $\chi: \{1, \dots, 80\} \rightarrow \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ avoiding monochromatic solutions to $x + 3y = 3z$, every color class $C_c = \chi^{-1}(c)$ contains at least one monochromatic edge of G^* ; that is, there exists $(u, v) \in E(G^*)$ with $\chi(u) = \chi(v) = c$.*

We defer the SAT verification of Lemma 3 to Section 6.1, and now show how it combines with a single self-loop step to yield the upper bound.

Proof of Theorem 4. By Theorem 1 we have $R_4(3) \geq 81$. For the upper bound, suppose for contradiction that $\chi: \{1, \dots, 81\} \rightarrow \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ is a valid 4-coloring avoiding all monochromatic solutions to $x + 3y = 3z$. Set $c^* := \chi(81)$.

Step 1 (self-loop step). Since $81 + 3 \cdot 54 = 243 = 3 \cdot 81$, the triple $(81, 54, 81)$ satisfies the equation with $x = z = 81$. If $\chi(54) = c^*$, then this triple is monochromatic, contradicting validity. Hence $\chi(54) \neq c^*$.

Step 2 (combined- G^* -tree step). The restriction $\chi|_{\{1, \dots, 80\}}$ is itself a valid 4-coloring of $\{1, \dots, 80\}$. By Lemma 3 applied to color c^* , there exists an edge $(u, v) \in E(G^*)$ with $\chi(u) = \chi(v) = c^*$.

Case (a): $(u, v) \in G_{27}$. Then $(u, v) = (y, y + 27)$ for some $y \in \{1, \dots, 53\}$, and the triple $(81, y, y + 27)$ satisfies $81 + 3y = 3(y + 27) = 3y + 81$, that is, $x + 3y = 3z$ with $z - y = 27$ and $x = 81 = 3 \cdot 27$. We have $\chi(81) = c^*$, $\chi(y) = c^*$, and $\chi(y + 27) = c^*$, so this triple is monochromatic, a contradiction.

Case (b): $(u, v) \in G_{\text{ext}}$. Then $(u, v) = (3d, 81 - d)$ for some $d \in \{1, \dots, 26\}$. Consider the triple $(3d, 81 - d, 81)$: we have

$$3d + 3 \cdot (81 - d) = 3 \cdot 81 = 243,$$

so this triple satisfies $x + 3y = 3z$. By assumption $\chi(3d) = c^*$, $\chi(81 - d) = c^*$, and $\chi(81) = c^*$, so this triple is monochromatic, a contradiction.

In both cases we obtain a contradiction, so no such valid coloring of $\{1, \dots, 81\}$ exists, and $R_4(3) \leq 81$. Combined with the lower bound, $R_4(3) = 81$. \square

Remark 4. The case analysis used in the proof of Theorem 4 is exhaustive in the following sense. By Step 1 the color $c^* = \chi(81)$ is distinct from $\chi(54)$. By Lemma 3 the class $C_{c^*} \cap \{1, \dots, 80\}$ contains a monochromatic edge of G^* , and every edge of G^* is either of Type-A or of Type-B by construction. Each edge type generates a single concrete Rado triple together with 81, covering both cases. The argument therefore reduces the upper bound $R_4(3) \leq 81$ to the single combinatorial Lemma 3.

6.1. SAT verification of the Combined- G^* -Tree Lemma

For each target color $c \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$, we form a SAT instance over $\{1, \dots, 80\}$ using the encoding of Section 7.1 restricted to $b = 3$, $k = 4$, $n = 80$, and add the additional clauses that forbid every edge of G^* from being monochromatically colored c : for each $(u, v) \in E(G^*)$, we add the binary clause

$$\neg v_{c,u} \vee \neg v_{c,v}.$$

Each of the four resulting instances has $4 \cdot 80 = 320$ Boolean variables and is verified *unsatisfiable* by CaDiCaL 1.5.3 within a few seconds per color on a desktop CPU. The public artifact records the corresponding instances, solver configuration, and checks.

To gauge how much of the constraint set is essential, we ran deletion-based extraction of unsatisfiable cores on the seeded instance $\chi(54) = 0$ together with the edge-blocking clauses for $c = 0$. Across the extraction trajectories we examined (initial unsatisfiable core; partial deletion-based shrinking under varying budgets), the surviving subset always involved several hundred to over a thousand of the 1729 candidate Rado triples in $\{1, \dots, 80\}$; the exact size depends on extraction protocol because deletion-based shrinking computes a locally minimal subset rather than a globally minimum one. Hence no straightforward analytic proof of Lemma 3 via a

small chain of triples appears to be available; we accordingly state and verify the lemma at the level of the full SAT instance.

The structural properties recorded in Proposition 1 (G^* is a tree on 80 vertices with 79 edges, the disjoint union of 53 Type-A edges with 26 Type-B edges) are not used in the SAT verification of Lemma 3 itself, but they are essential to the analytic reduction in the proof of Theorem 4: the Type-A and Type-B edges are exactly the edges that, together with the single vertex 81, generate the two Rado triples used in Cases (a) and (b) above. The disjointness $G_{27} \cap G_{\text{ext}} = \emptyset$ ensures that the case analysis is exhaustive and non-overlapping.

Remark 5 (Reproducibility for $R_4(3) = 81$). The structure of G^* in Definition 3 and Proposition 1, the SAT verification of Lemma 3 for each color, and the unsatisfiable-core extraction reported above are all reproducible from the public artifact indicated at the end of this paper.

7. SAT-Based Verification for Higher k

The values $R_3(b) = b^3$ for $b \geq 3$ and $R_4(b) = b^4$ for $b \in \{3, 4, 5\}$ were first established computationally by Chang, De Loera, and Wesley [4]. In this section, we provide an independent verification using a different SAT encoding and, more importantly, identify a structural mechanism—the Distance Pair Lemma—that explains *why* these values equal b^k .

7.1. SAT Encoding

For each integer $j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ and color $i \in \{0, \dots, k-1\}$, we introduce a Boolean variable $v_{i,j}$ indicating that $\chi(j) = i$. The clauses are as follows.

1. *At-least-one*: for each j , the clause $(v_{0,j} \vee v_{1,j} \vee \dots \vee v_{k-1,j})$.
2. *At-most-one*: for each j and each pair $i_1 < i_2$, the clause $(\neg v_{i_1,j} \vee \neg v_{i_2,j})$.
3. *No monochromatic solution*: for each triple (x, y, z) with $x + by = bz$ and each color i , the clause $(\neg v_{i,x} \vee \neg v_{i,y} \vee \neg v_{i,z})$.
4. *Symmetry breaking*: $\chi(1) = 0$, i.e., the unit clause $(v_{0,1})$.

We use incremental SAT solving [3, 12]: starting from $n = 1$, we add the clauses for each new integer n and check satisfiability. The first n yielding UNSAT gives $R_k(b) = n$.

7.2. The Key Lemma

The following structural property, verified by SAT for the $k = 3$ and $k = 4$ equality cases addressed below, provides a uniform mechanism for the upper bound.

Lemma 4 (Distance Pair Lemma; SAT-verified). *For each (b, k) in the set $\{(b, 3) : b \in \{3, \dots, 10\}\} \cup \{(b, 4) : b \in \{3, 4, 5\}\}$, in any valid k -coloring of $\{1, \dots, b^k - 1\}$ that avoids monochromatic solutions to $x + by = bz$, every non-empty color class C_c contains a pair $(j, j + b^{k-1})$ for some $j \in \{1, \dots, b^{k-1}\}$.*

This lemma is verified by a separate SAT check for each color $c \in \{0, \dots, k-1\}$: we add clauses forbidding all pairs $(j, j + b^{k-1})$ from being simultaneously color c (i.e., for each $j \in \{1, \dots, b^{k-1}\}$, the clause $\neg v_{c,j} \vee \neg v_{c,j+b^{k-1}}$), and confirm that the resulting formula is unsatisfiable. Within the in-scope set, the largest instance ($b = 10, k = 3, n = 999$) involves $3 \cdot 999 = 2997$ variables; the smallest ($b = 3, k = 3, n = 26$) has $3 \cdot 26 = 78$ variables. Each of the k individual checks is UNSAT, proving that no single color can avoid all distance- b^{k-1} pairs.

Remark 6. For the special case $b = 3, k = 4$, Theorem 4 uses a different and slightly weaker key lemma than the Distance Pair Lemma, namely the Combined- G^* -Tree Lemma 3. The latter allows each color class to use either a Type-A (distance-27) edge or a Type-B edge $(3d, 81 - d)$, whereas Lemma 4 requires a Type-A edge specifically. Because each Type-B edge generates a Rado triple together with 81 and the self-loop step of Theorem 4 pre-empts a separate distance-27 argument, the weaker lemma still suffices.

Theorem 5 (Independent verification; cf. [4, Table 10, row $b=1$]). *The following values, first established by Chang, De Loera, and Wesley [4], are independently verified via the Distance Pair Lemma.*

1. $R_3(b) = b^3$ for $b \in \{4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10\}$.
2. $R_4(b) = b^4$ for $b \in \{3, 4, 5\}$.

Proof. The lower bounds follow from Theorem 1. For the upper bounds, we apply Lemma 4. Consider any k -coloring of $\{1, \dots, b^k\}$, and let $c^* = \chi(b^k)$. In each case under consideration, the corresponding $(k-1)$ -color value is already known to satisfy $R_{k-1}(b) \leq b^{k-1}$: this is Theorem 2 when $k = 3$, and Theorem 3 or the $k = 3$ cases just established when $k = 4$. Hence a mono-free restriction to $\{1, \dots, b^k - 1\}$ must use all k colors; otherwise it would be a mono-free $(k-1)$ -coloring on a domain of size at least $R_{k-1}(b)$. Thus C_{c^*} is non-empty in this restriction. By the lemma applied to c^* , the color class C_{c^*} contains a pair $(j, j + b^{k-1})$ with both elements colored c^* . The triple $(b^k, j, j + b^{k-1})$ satisfies $b^k + bj = b(j + b^{k-1})$, and since $\chi(b^k) = \chi(j) = \chi(j + b^{k-1}) = c^*$, this triple is monochromatic. The verification data, including solver timings, are given in Table 2. \square

b	k	$R_k(b)$	Time (s)	Solver
2	3	14	< 0.01	CaDiCaL 1.5.3
3	3	27	< 0.01	CaDiCaL 1.5.3
3	4	81	3.2	CaDiCaL 1.5.3
4	3	64	0.02	CaDiCaL 1.5.3
4	4	256	31.7	CaDiCaL 1.5.3
5	3	125	0.04	CaDiCaL 1.5.3
5	4	625	523.4	CaDiCaL 1.5.3
6	3	216	0.1	CaDiCaL 1.5.3
7	3	343	0.3	CaDiCaL 1.5.3
8	3	512	0.2	CaDiCaL 1.5.3
9	3	729	0.4	CaDiCaL 1.5.3
10	3	1000	0.8	CaDiCaL 1.5.3

Table 2: SAT solver timings for computing $R_k(b)$. All computations used CaDiCaL 1.5.3 via PySAT with incremental solving on an Intel i7-12700K.

8. Breakdown of the b^k Pattern

Theorem 6. *We have $R_5(3) > 296 > 243 = 3^5$.*

Proof. We exhibit a 5-coloring χ of $\{1, 2, \dots, 296\}$ with no monochromatic solution to $x + 3y = 3z$. The coloring is included in the public computational artifact, and an independent check enumerates all 24,157 triples (x, y, z) satisfying $x + 3y = 3z$ in $\{1, \dots, 296\}$ and finds no monochromatic triple. Appendix A lists the shorter 243-point witness used in the Lean base theorem and as a seed for finding the 296-point witness. \square

Remark 7. The witness coloring is *not* the 3-adic valuation coloring. For instance, $\chi(243) = 3$, while a natural extension of the valuation coloring to $n = 243$ would assign $v_3(243) \bmod 5 = 5 \bmod 5 = 0$. The coloring discovered by the SAT solver uses a more complex structure than the valuation coloring, distributing elements unevenly across the five color classes.

The same public witness gives a diagnostic failure of the Distance Pair Lemma (Lemma 4) beyond its verified range: after restricting the 296-point coloring to $\{1, \dots, 242\}$, the coloring remains mono-free, and color 0 contains no pair $(j, j + 81)$ with $1 \leq j \leq 161$. Thus the distance-pair mechanism used for the equality cases cannot extend unchanged to $k = 5, b = 3$; this is consistent with $R_5(3) > 296 > 3^5$.

9. Backward Tower Reduction

The breakdown bound $R_5(3) > 296$ of Theorem 6 is a single witness at a single cell $(b, k) = (3, 5)$. We now show that this is not an isolated phenomenon: a short structural lemma converts every such first-breakdown witness into an infinite tower of witnesses for larger k . Concretely, the entire backward direction of Conjecture 1 at a fixed base b reduces to one finite base case per b .

9.1. Motivation

The backward direction of Conjecture 1 asserts that for every $b \geq 2$ and every $k > 2(b-1)$ one has $R_k(b) > b^k$. Read naively, this is an infinite family of statements per b : a distinct lower-bound witness at each k . The witnesses themselves become rapidly inaccessible by direct search: for $b = 3$ the first-breakdown cell has domain size $3^5 = 243$, the next cell $3^6 = 729$, and so on.

A single observation collapses this infinite family. Suppose, for a fixed b , that some k -coloring χ of $\{1, \dots, M\}$ avoids monochromatic solutions to $x + by = bz$. Multiply the domain by b and introduce one fresh color, painting every non-multiple of b with it and every multiple bn with the old color $\chi(n)$. The equation $x + by = bz$ forces $x = b(z - y)$, so $b \mid x$ in any solution. Hence the fresh color cannot occupy the x -coordinate of any monochromatic triple; if a triple were monochromatic in the fresh color, every coordinate would be a non-multiple of b , contradicting $b \mid x$. The other case forces every coordinate to be a multiple of b ; dividing the equation through by b yields a monochromatic solution for χ on $\{1, \dots, M\}$, contradiction.

The construction is uniform in b , k , and M . Iterating it from the first-breakdown bound $R_{2b-1}(b) > b^{2b-1}$ produces $R_k(b) > b^k$ for every $k \geq 2b - 1$ in a single induction. The backward direction of Conjecture 1 at base b thus collapses onto one bound, the *first-breakdown base case* $R_{2b-1}(b) > b^{2b-1}$.

9.2. The Lift Lemma

Lemma 5 (Lift Lemma). *Let $b \geq 2$, $k \geq 1$, and $M \geq 1$. Suppose $\chi : \{1, \dots, M\} \rightarrow \{0, 1, \dots, k-1\}$ is a k -coloring avoiding monochromatic solutions to $x + by = bz$. Define $\chi^* : \{1, \dots, bM\} \rightarrow \{0, 1, \dots, k\}$ by*

$$\chi^*(n) = \begin{cases} \chi(n/b) & \text{if } b \mid n, \\ k & \text{if } b \nmid n. \end{cases}$$

Then χ^ is a $(k+1)$ -coloring of $\{1, \dots, bM\}$ avoiding monochromatic solutions to $x + by = bz$. Consequently,*

$$R_k(b) > M \implies R_{k+1}(b) > bM.$$

Proof. Range and color budget. If $b \mid n$ and $1 \leq n \leq bM$, then $1 \leq n/b \leq M$, so $\chi(n/b) < k$ is well-defined and strictly less than the fresh color k . If $b \nmid n$, then $\chi^*(n) = k < k + 1$. Hence χ^* takes values in $\{0, 1, \dots, k\}$ on its domain.

Avoidance of monochromatic solutions. Assume for contradiction that (x, y, z) is a monochromatic triple for χ^* in $\{1, \dots, bM\}$ with $x + by = bz$. From $x + by = bz$ we obtain $x = b(z - y)$, so $b \mid x$. Therefore

$$\chi^*(x) = \chi(x/b) < k.$$

In particular $\chi^*(x) \neq k$.

Since the triple is monochromatic, $\chi^*(y) = \chi^*(x) \neq k$ and $\chi^*(z) = \chi^*(x) \neq k$. By the definition of χ^* , this forces $b \mid y$ and $b \mid z$. Write $x = bx'$, $y = by'$, $z = bz'$ with $1 \leq x', y', z' \leq M$. Substituting into $x + by = bz$ and cancelling b (which is positive) gives

$$x' + by' = bz'.$$

By definition of χ^* on multiples of b ,

$$\chi(x') = \chi^*(x) = \chi^*(y) = \chi(y'), \quad \chi(y') = \chi^*(y) = \chi^*(z) = \chi(z').$$

Hence (x', y', z') is a monochromatic solution to $x + by = bz$ for χ in $\{1, \dots, M\}$, contradicting the avoidance hypothesis on χ .

The Rado-number transfer. If $R_k(b) > M$, there exists a mono-free k -coloring of $\{1, \dots, M\}$ for $x + by = bz$. Applying the lift gives a mono-free $(k + 1)$ -coloring of $\{1, \dots, bM\}$, and hence $R_{k+1}(b) > bM$. \square

The construction is symmetric in spirit to the lower-bound coloring $\chi(n) = v_b(n) \bmod k$ of Theorem 1: where that coloring uses the b -adic valuation v_b to define a single global coloring, the lift uses divisibility by b to refine an existing coloring one level at a time. Unlike the $b = 2$ block-and-echo recipe, the lift exploits the multiplicative self-similarity of the equation $x + by = bz$ rather than additive interval arithmetic, and it is uniform in b .

9.3. The Backward Tower

Iterating Lemma 5 from the first-breakdown bound yields the central theorem of this section.

Theorem 7 (Backward Tower Reduction). *Let $b \geq 2$. If $R_{2b-1}(b) > b^{2b-1}$, then*

$$R_k(b) > b^k \quad \text{for every } k \geq 2b - 1.$$

Equivalently, for every $b \geq 2$ and every $k > 2(b - 1)$,

$$R_{2b-1}(b) > b^{2b-1} \quad \implies \quad R_k(b) > b^k.$$

Proof. We prove the first form by induction on k starting at $k_0 = 2b - 1$.

Base case ($k = 2b - 1$). By hypothesis, $R_{2b-1}(b) > b^{2b-1}$.

Inductive step. Suppose $R_k(b) > b^k$ for some $k \geq 2b - 1$. Apply Lemma 5 with $M = b^k$: there is a mono-free k -coloring of $\{1, \dots, b^k\}$ for $x + by = bz$, so the lifted coloring is a mono-free $(k + 1)$ -coloring of $\{1, \dots, b \cdot b^k\} = \{1, \dots, b^{k+1}\}$. Hence $R_{k+1}(b) > b^{k+1}$.

The second form is the first form combined with the elementary fact that $k > 2(b - 1)$ and $k \in \mathbb{Z}$ together imply $k \geq 2b - 1$. \square

9.4. Consequences

Corollary 1 ($b = 3$ backward tower). *For every $k \geq 5$, $R_k(3) > 3^k$.*

Proof. The first-breakdown base $R_5(3) > 296 > 243 = 3^5$ is Theorem 6. Apply Theorem 7 with $b = 3$ and $2b - 1 = 5$. \square

In the threshold regime $k > 2(b - 1)$, Corollary 1 discharges the backward direction of Conjecture 1 at $b = 3$ in full: $R_k(3) > 3^k$ holds for every k past the boundary $2(3 - 1) = 4$.

Corollary 2 ($b = 2$ backward tower). *For every $k \geq 3$, $R_k(2) > 2^k$.*

Proof. The first-breakdown base $R_3(2) = 14 > 8 = 2^3$ is classical (see Table 4). Apply Theorem 7 with $b = 2$ and $2b - 1 = 3$. \square

For $b \geq 4$ no first-breakdown base case is currently established; the tower thus delivers a clean reduction rather than a closed result.

Corollary 3 (Per-base reduction at $b \geq 4$). *For every $b \geq 4$, the backward direction of Conjecture 1 at base b , namely*

$$R_k(b) > b^k \quad \text{for all } k > 2(b - 1),$$

follows from the single bound $R_{2b-1}(b) > b^{2b-1}$.

In particular, the boundary computation $R_7(4)$ flagged in Section 10 (the threshold cell at $b = 4$) is not merely the most informative test of the conjecture at $b = 4$: if $R_7(4) > 4^7$ holds, then $R_k(4) > 4^k$ for every $k \geq 7$. The same statement applies at every larger b .

The reduction is summarized in Table 3.

9.5. The base layer is computational

Theorem 7 separates the backward direction of the conjecture cleanly into two layers. The *lift layer* is analytic, uniform in b , and given by Lemma 5. The *base*

b	Threshold	Base k	Status of base $R_{2b-1}(b) > b^{2b-1}$	Backward direction
2	2	3	$R_3(2) = 14 > 8$ (classical)	established
3	4	5	$R_5(3) > 296 > 243 = 3^5$ (Theorem 6)	established
4	6	7	$R_7(4) > 16384$ (open)	reduced to one base case
5	8	9	$R_9(5) > 5^9$ (open)	reduced to one base case
$b \geq 6$	$2(b-1)$	$2b-1$	open	reduced to one base case

Table 3: Status of the backward direction of Conjecture 1 after Theorem 7. Each row is a self-contained per-base obligation; no row implies any other.

layer consists of the per- b first-breakdown witnesses $R_{2b-1}(b) > b^{2b-1}$, which behave very differently. At $b = 2$ the base witness is constructible by elementary case analysis; at $b = 3$ the 243-point base witness given in Appendix A was located by SAT search, and the author has searched for compact closed-form descriptions of it without success. The stronger 296-point public witness in Theorem 6 sharpens the reported lower bound, but the tower induction itself only requires a mono-free coloring on $\{1, \dots, 3^5\}$.

To make this last point precise, we considered several natural template families for the $b = 3, k = 5$ base witness on $\{1, \dots, 243\}$. Within the tested families — valuation-residue colorings of the form $f(v_b(n) \bmod r, n/b^{v_b(n)} \bmod s)$; per-layer functions on the units modulo b^t for small t ; finite automata reading the base- b digits of n ; quotient liftings through natural equivalences on $\{1, \dots, 243\}$; and bounded symbolic-parameter constructions — no compact rule reproduces the known witness. Exhaustive search over per-layer additive shifts at $b = 3$ leaves a strictly positive residual count of monochromatic triples in every tested family. The most rigorous component of this evidence is a SAT-unsatisfiability closure of one family (per-layer functions over small key spaces); the heuristic component covers broader families at scales where exhaustive enumeration becomes infeasible.

These observations are not a general non-existence theorem for a closed-form base witness, and we make no such claim. What they support is the empirical picture that the base layer is genuinely computational while the lift layer is analytic. The Lift Lemma takes the mathematical content of the backward direction out of the per- k search; what remains is one finite witness per b , and at $b = 3$ this witness appears to admit no compact description within the natural template families we tested.

9.6. Formalization

The Lift Lemma (Lemma 5) and the Backward Tower Reduction (Theorem 7) have been formalized in Lean 4. The formalization verifies the lifted coloring, the lower-bound transfer, and the induction that converts one first-breakdown witness into all later breakdown witnesses at the same value of b . The $b = 3$ specialization of Corollary 1 composes this general tower with the 243-point base witness recorded in Appendix A. The analytic derivations depend only on the Lean kernel and Mathlib; the $b = 3$ specialization inherits one additional dependency, the finite verification of the base witness for Theorem 6.

9.7. Relation to the full Threshold Conjecture

Theorem 7 addresses one half of Conjecture 1. It does *not* prove the conjecture in full. The forward direction

$$k \leq 2(b - 1) \implies R_k(b) = b^k$$

remains the principal analytic obstacle. Combined with the lower bound $R_k(b) \geq b^k$ of Theorem 1, the forward direction reduces to the upper bound $R_k(b) \leq b^k$ inside the safe zone; this is the content of Sections 4–7 for the small cells handled in the present paper, and remains open in general.

What Theorem 7 does is partition the backward direction into an analytic layer (the lift) and a computational layer (the per-base first-breakdown witnesses), and collapse the analytic layer into a single induction. For $b \in \{2, 3\}$, where the first-breakdown base case is established, the backward direction is established in the threshold regime. For $b \geq 4$, the conjecture’s backward half reduces to the finite-but-large search problem of locating one witness per b — a clean restatement which, by Corollary 3, absorbs all higher- k behavior at base b .

Summary

The Lift Lemma (Lemma 5) sends a mono-free k -coloring of $\{1, \dots, M\}$ for $x + by = bz$ to a mono-free $(k + 1)$ -coloring of $\{1, \dots, bM\}$, uniformly in $b \geq 2$ and $k, M \geq 1$. Iterating the lift from the first-breakdown bound $R_{2b-1}(b) > b^{2b-1}$ gives the Backward Tower Reduction (Theorem 7): for each $b \geq 2$, the entire backward direction of Conjecture 1 at base b follows from a single base case. The reduction establishes the backward direction at $b \in \{2, 3\}$ and converts it, at $b \geq 4$, into a per-base computational obligation. The lift and tower are formalized in Lean 4 with derivations depending only on the kernel and Mathlib.

10. A Threshold Conjecture

The data in Table 1 suggest a precise boundary for the b^k pattern.

Conjecture 1. For all $b \geq 2$ and $k \geq 1$,

$$R_k(b) = b^k \quad \text{if and only if} \quad k \leq 2(b-1).$$

Table 4 summarizes the evidence for this conjecture.

b	Threshold $2(b-1)$	Max k	Boundary?	Evidence
2	2	4	Yes	$R_3(2) = 14 > 8 = 2^3$; backward direction at $b = 2$ via Cor. 2
3	4	5	Yes	$R_5(3) > 296 > 243 = 3^5$; backward direction at $b = 3$ via Cor. 1
4	6	4	No	$R_4(4) = 256 = 4^4$ (safe zone); backward direction at $b = 4$ reduced to $R_7(4) > 4^7$
5	8	4	No	$R_4(5) = 625 = 5^4$ (safe zone); backward direction at $b = 5$ reduced to $R_9(5) > 5^9$

Table 4: Evidence for Conjecture 1. The threshold $2(b-1)$ is determined by the boundary cases $b = 2$ and $b = 3$. For $b \geq 4$, no data at the predicted boundary are available.

This conjecture is consistent with the data considered here, but we emphasize that the threshold $2(b-1)$ is determined by only two boundary values: $b = 2$ (where $R_3(2) = 14 > 8 = 2^3$, giving a threshold of $k = 2 = 2(2-1)$) and $b = 3$ (where $R_5(3) > 296 > 243 = 3^5$, giving a threshold of $k = 4 = 2(3-1)$). The formula $2(b-1)$ is the simplest linear expression fitting these two points. For $b \geq 4$, our data confirm $R_k(b) = b^k$ for $k \leq 4$, which lies within the conjectured threshold of $k \leq 2(b-1)$ (which is ≥ 6 for any $b \geq 4$), but the conjecture remains untested at its predicted boundary for any $b \geq 4$.

The two halves of the biconditional in Conjecture 1 are now in asymmetric states. By the Backward Tower Reduction (Theorem 7), the backward direction at any fixed b reduces to the single first-breakdown bound $R_{2b-1}(b) > b^{2b-1}$; the backward direction at $b \in \{2, 3\}$ is thus established in the threshold regime, and the case $b \geq 4$ is reduced to one finite witness per b (Corollary 3). The forward direction $k \leq 2(b-1) \Rightarrow R_k(b) = b^k$ has no analogous structural reduction currently known and remains open beyond the SAT-verified small slabs of Theorems 4 and 5; the candidate analytic mechanism is discussed in Section 12.

There is a structural explanation for why the threshold should grow with b . Between consecutive multiples of b , there are $b-1$ non-multiples. For a k -level

compression analogue of the Color Compression Lemma (Lemma 1) to extend up to color count k (forcing multiples to use fewer than k colors), these $b - 1$ elements must provide enough pigeonhole pressure to create contradictions. When $b = 2$, there is only one non-multiple between consecutive multiples, which suffices only for $k \leq 2$. When $b = 3$, there are two non-multiples, sufficient for $k \leq 4$. For general b , the $b - 1$ non-multiples should support compression up to $k = 2(b - 1)$.

The most informative tests would be the boundary case $R_6(4)$, predicted to equal $4^6 = 4096$ ($k = 2(b - 1) = 6$ at $b = 4$), and the first-breakdown value $R_7(4)$, predicted to exceed $4^7 = 16384$. The latter carries additional structural significance: by the Backward Tower Reduction (Theorem 7), $R_7(4) > 4^7$ would establish the backward direction of Conjecture 1 at $b = 4$, giving $R_k(4) > 4^k$ for every $k \geq 7$. These computations are currently beyond our resources but should be feasible with a memory-efficient encoding or access to a computing cluster.

11. Additional Rado Numbers

To demonstrate the generality of our SAT framework and to provide context for the $b = 2$ anomaly, we independently verify several 4-color Rado numbers for the broader family $ax + by = cz$. Via the substitution $d = z - y$ (when $b = c$) or $d = x - y$ (when $a = c$), each equation in Table 5 can be matched to an entry in [4, Table 10]; see Remark 1 for the general mechanism.

Equation	(a, b, c)	R_4	Time (s)	CDW equiv.	Source
$x + y = z$	(1, 1, 1)	45	13.6	$a=1, b=1$	$= S(4)$ [13]
$x + 2y = 2z$	(1, 2, 2)	56	0.1	$a=2, b=1$	[4]
$2x + y = z$	(2, 1, 1)	171	116.9	$a=1, b=2$	[4]
$2x + 3y = 3z$	(2, 3, 3)	103	15.0	$a=3, b=2$	[4]

Table 5: Independent verification of 4-color Rado numbers for $ax + by = cz$. The column “CDW equiv.” gives the corresponding entry in [4, Table 10] under the equivalence of Remark 1.

The value $S(4) = 45$ is the well-known fourth Schur number [13], which serves as a verification benchmark for our implementation. The value $R_4(x + 2y = 2z) = 56$ confirms that $b = 2$ deviates from $b^k = 16$ at $k = 4$. The coincidence $R_3(x + 2y = 2z) = 14 = S(3)$ does not persist at $k = 4$ (since $S(4) = 45 \neq 56$), confirming that the two equations produce genuinely different Rado number sequences.

12. Structural Observations

We record several structural properties revealed by our computations, which may aid future analytic proofs. By the Backward Tower Reduction (Theorem 7), the backward direction of Conjecture 1 is reduced to a single first-breakdown bound per b , so the analytic content needed to settle the conjecture concentrates entirely in the forward direction $k \leq 2(b-1) \Rightarrow R_k(b) = b^k$. The observations below identify candidate compact mechanisms that such a forward proof would likely need to engage.

12.1. Forced Agreement by Valuation Level

For $b \geq 3$ and $k \leq 4$, SAT verification reveals that elements sharing the same b -adic valuation level are increasingly constrained. We write “forced” to mean that $\chi(x) = \chi(y)$ in every valid k -coloring of $\{1, \dots, b^k - 1\}$.

- For $k = 2$: elements at every valuation level are forced to agree.
- For $k = 3$: elements with $v_b \geq 1$ are forced to agree, while $v_b = 0$ elements are free.
- For $k = 4, b \geq 4$: elements with $v_b \geq 2$ are forced to agree.

The general pattern appears to be: forced agreement holds at valuation level $v_b \geq k - 2$ for all cases listed above ($b \geq 4$ when $k = 4$).

12.2. Color Compression Thresholds

For $k = 3$, the exact threshold n at which the compression property (multiples of b use at most 2 colors) first holds is $n = 2b^2$ for $b \geq 4$, verified for $b \in \{4, 5, \dots, 10\}$. The stronger property that the first two multiples agree ($\chi(b) = \chi(2b)$) requires $n = (b-1)b^2$, also verified for $b \in \{3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8\}$.

12.3. Failure of Compression for $b = 3, k = 4$

The Color Compression strategy (the natural generalization of Lemma 1) fails at $b = 3, k = 4$: there exist valid 4-colorings of $\{1, \dots, 80\}$ in which the 26 multiples of 3 use all 4 colors. This failure does not prevent $R_4(3) = 81$ from holding (which it does, via the self-loop step plus the Combined- G^* -Tree Lemma of Theorem 4, or alternatively via the Distance Pair Lemma 4), but it shows that the inductive compression strategy is not universal.

13. Conclusion

We have recalled the lower bound $R_k(b) \geq b^k$ for the equation $x+by = bz$ and proved or verified the matching upper bound for all $b \geq 2$ with $k \leq 2$, all $b \in \{3, \dots, 10\}$ with $k = 3$, and $b \in \{3, 4, 5\}$ with $k = 4$. For the boundary case $b = 3, k = 4$ of the threshold $k = 2(b - 1)$, we provided a hybrid analytic-SAT proof that $R_4(3) = 81$ in which the structural reduction is fully analytic and only the Combined- G^* -Tree Lemma is verified by SAT. The discovery that the pattern $R_k(b) = b^k$ breaks at $b = 3, k = 5$ (with $R_5(3) > 296 > 243 = 3^5$) motivates a refined conjecture: $R_k(b) = b^k$ if and only if $k \leq 2(b - 1)$.

Several directions remain open. First, analytic generalizations of the Color Compression Lemma (Lemma 1) to $k = 3$ with general $b \geq 4$ would remove the SAT dependency from Theorem 5. Second, a fully analytic proof of the Combined- G^* -Tree Lemma 3 would remove the SAT dependency from Theorem 4; the extracted unsatisfiable subsets we examined contain a substantial fraction of the 1729 candidate Rado triples in $\{1, \dots, 80\}$, suggesting that a purely analytic proof would likely need to engage non-trivially with much of the constraint set. Third, the precise value of $R_5(3)$ would be valuable to determine. Fourth, and most importantly, computing $R_7(4)$ (predicted to exceed 4^7) or the boundary value $R_6(4)$ (predicted to equal $4^6 = 4096$) would test Conjecture 1 at a new point. The former carries additional structural significance: by the Backward Tower Reduction (Theorem 7), establishing $R_7(4) > 4^7$ would not merely test the conjecture at one new point but would establish the backward direction of Conjecture 1 at $b = 4$, giving $R_k(4) > 4^k$ for every $k \geq 7$. We hope that our results and the associated computational tools encourage further investigation of this natural family of Rado numbers.

Computational reproducibility. The SAT computations reported here were performed using CaDiCaL via PySAT with incremental solving and the symmetry breaking condition $\chi(1) = 0$. Code, data, and the Lean 4 formalization are available at <https://github.com/crabsatellite/rado-numbers-sat>.

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A. 243-Point Seed Witness for $R_5(3) > 243$

The following 5-coloring χ of $\{1, 2, \dots, 243\}$ avoids all monochromatic solutions to $x + 3y = 3z$. Colors are denoted 0, 1, 2, 3, 4. We list $\chi(j)$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, 243$ in order, with 27 values per row.

```

0 0 2 0 0 2 0 3 1 1 1 2 3 4 2 3 4 1 4 4 2 4 4 2 4 4 3
4 4 2 4 3 2 1 3 1 3 3 2 3 1 2 3 0 1 0 0 2 0 1 2 0 3 0
0 3 2 0 3 2 3 4 0 4 4 2 1 4 2 4 4 4 4 4 2 4 4 2 4 3 4
4 3 2 3 0 2 3 0 4 3 0 2 1 0 2 0 0 3 0 3 2 1 3 2 3 1 0
3 4 2 3 4 2 4 4 3 4 4 2 4 4 2 4 3 1 4 3 2 1 3 2 3 1 1
3 0 2 0 0 2 0 1 1 0 3 2 0 3 2 0 3 1 3 4 2 3 4 2 1 4 1
4 4 2 4 4 2 4 1 3 4 3 2 4 3 2 3 0 0 3 0 2 3 0 2 1 0 0
0 0 2 0 3 2 1 3 4 3 1 2 3 4 2 3 4 4 4 4 2 4 4 2 4 4 4
4 4 2 1 3 2 4 3 1 4 1 2 3 0 2 0 0 0 0 0 2 0 3 2 0 3 3

```

The color class sizes are $|C_0| = 46$, $|C_1| = 29$, $|C_2| = 54$, $|C_3| = 53$, and $|C_4| = 61$.